

Cenni *et al*² have reported that azo frequencies were usually observed in the range of 1570-1595 cm^{-1} . Bands in the region 1472-1545 cm^{-1} have been attributed to a number of aryl azo compounds of Mo by King³. In the ligand OHBAN, we obtain the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ band at 1550 cm^{-1} . In the adducts, this band shifts down to 1540-1515 cm^{-1} suggesting that the $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ group is probably associated to the metal. These bands also split in the adducts which may be due to a change in symmetry. The $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ frequency of ligand and its compounds with alkali metal salts have been given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR FREQUENCIES OF LIGAND AND ADDUCTS

Compound	$-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ frequency (cm^{-1})
OHBAN=L	1550
NaIN2N.L	1540, 1585 ¹
KIN2N.L	1540, 1585
NaSHQ.L	1540, 1585
KSHQ.L	1535, 1530
NaONP.L	1540
KONP.L	1540
Na2H3NA.L	1535
K2H3NA.L	1535, 1530
Na.anth.L	1525, 1510
K.anth.L	1545, 1535
NaSalH.L	1540, 1525

The OH stretching frequency of the ligand has been observed at $\sim 3360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. It shifts down to $\sim 3220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the compounds thereby showing the involvement of $-\text{OH}$ in the formation of adducts. The $\text{H}-\text{O}-\text{H}$ bending mode is seen at $\sim 1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand, while in the compounds two peaks at $\sim 1320-1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $\sim 1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed. The extra peaks in complexes may justify their formation.

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Conductometric and Spectrometric Studies on Complexes of Ag(I) and Hg(II) Ions with N,N'-Diphenyl Thiourea

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SINCE N,N'-diphenylthiourea contains two phenyl substituent groups, the complexation behaviour of this ligand decreases¹⁻³ because of the electron withdrawing tendency of the phenyl group. In

view of this, complexing behaviour of this ligand with Ag(I) and Hg(II) ions have been investigated in solution by conductometric titration and in solid state by infrared spectroscopy and the results are reported here.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. N,N'-Diphenylthiourea was prepared by standard method⁴. The prepared compound gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Preparation of complexes: The diaquo N,N'-diphenylthiourea silver(I) nitrate polymeric complex, $\{[\text{Ag}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{DPhTU})]\text{NO}_3\}_n$, was prepared by simply mixing an aqueous solution of AgNO_3 with ethanolic solution of N,N'-diphenylthiourea in 1 : 2 molar ratio. A green coloured precipitate formed immediately which was digested on water bath for 30 min. The complex was thereafter filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried at 110° . (Found : C, 35.90 ; H, 3.45 ; N, 9.41 ; Ag, 24.84. Calcd. C, 35.94 ; H, 3.69 ; N, 9.69 ; Ag, 24.90%).

The green aquochloro N,N'-diphenylthiourea mercury(II) chloride complex, $\{[\text{Hg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{DPhTU})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}\}_n$, was prepared in the same manner as the Ag(I) complex. (Found : N, 5.84 ; Cl 13.43 ; Hg, 39.2%. Calcd. N, 5.41 ; Cl, 13.72 ; Hg, 39.8%).

Physical methods: The magnetic measurements were made at 30° using Guoy Balance. Both the complexes were found to be diamagnetic. The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin Elmer spectrophotometers, Model 521 and 621 in the range $4000-200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Conductometric titrations were carried out by means of Toshniwal conductometric bridge, model 302 using a dip type cell (cell constant $1.92 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mho/cm}^2$).

Results and Discussion

The analytical results indicate that empirical formula of the solid complexes are $\text{Ag}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{DPhTU})\text{NO}_3$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{DPhTU})\text{Cl}_2$. The conductometric titrations of 0.01 M AgNO_3 and 0.01 M HgCl_2 solutions were conducted against 0.005 M diphenyl urea solution and inflexion points for both titrations indicate the formation of 1 : 1 complexes.

The Ag(I) complex contains ionic nitrate. This has been confirmed by chemical method as well as by the infrared spectra of the complex. The infrared spectra of this complex exhibit a strong band at 1385 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 845 cm^{-1} . These bands are not present in the spectra of the diphenylthiourea ligand or of the Hg(II) complex. Since ionic nitrates exhibit⁵ strong infrared bands in the range of $1340-1410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and weak band in the range of $800-860 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, it may be suggested that nitrate group is in the ionic form in the Ag(I) complex. But as the complex is insoluble in almost all organic solvents, it may be tentatively assigned a polymeric

formula, $\{[Ag(H_2O)_2(DPhTU)]NO_3\}_n$. Out of the two chlorine atoms in $Hg(H_2O)(DPhTU)Cl_2$, one is ionic. This is confirmed by the presence of Cl^- ion in the Na_2CO_3 extract of the complex. The other Cl atom is covalently bonded. This is also confirmed by the presence of $\nu(Hg-Cl)$ (terminal) band at 325 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of this complex. $\nu(Hg-Cl)$ (terminal) bands are generally observed⁹⁻⁸ below this region in octahedral complexes. Thus, it may be concluded that Hg(II) ion is in tetrahedral coordination in this complex. But as the complex is insoluble in most organic solvents, the polymeric formulation, $\{[Hg(H_2O)(DPhTU)Cl]Cl\}_n$, may be suggested for it. The presence of coordinated water is confirmed⁹⁻¹⁰ by the presence of bands at $3440, 1640, 530, 515$ and 505 cm^{-1} in the Ag(I) complex and at $3500, 1645, 530, 515$ and 505 cm^{-1} in the Hg(II) complex. Out of these five bands, the first two are assigned to νH_2O and δH_2O and the latter three to vibrational mode of coordinated water. More than one vibrational modes also confirm the polymeric nature of the complexes.

The diphenylthiourea ligand is bonded to the Ag(I) and Hg(II) ions in the two complexes through nitrogen as well as through thiocarbonyl sulphur. This is confirmed from the following considerations. (i) The splitting of $\nu(N-H)$ band of the ligand (3210 cm^{-1}) into two distinct bands at 3300 cm^{-1} and 3100 cm^{-1} indicating coordination through nitrogen. (ii) The bands of the ligand at 1595 and 1540 cm^{-1} observed as strong bands are assigned to $\delta NH + \nu CN$ modes. There is no change in intensity and position of these bands. This is possible only when there is no coordination or coordination occurs through both nitrogen and sulphur. (iii) The thioamide band II of the ligand is observed at 1340 cm^{-1} and is mainly due to $\nu(C=S)$ mode of vibration. This band has red shifted to 1320 cm^{-1} in the Ag(I) complex and 1315 cm^{-1} in the Hg(II) complex. This indicates coordination through sulphur. (iv) The thioamide band IV is observed at 760 cm^{-1} as a weak band²⁰ in the infrared spectra of the ligand. This band is found at the same position in the spectra of the complexes but its intensity increases on coordination. As coordination through sulphur red shifts this band²¹⁻²² and coordination through nitrogen blue shifts it²¹⁻²², it may be concluded that bonding has taken place both through sulphur and nitrogen. Increase in intensity may be due to polymeric nature of the complexes. (v) The far infrared spectra of the ligand contain only one weak band at 485 cm^{-1} . But the infrared spectra of the Ag(I) complex contain weak bands at 555 and 380 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\nu Ag-OH_2$ and $\nu(Ag-N)$ modes of vibration. The infrared spectra of the Hg(II) complex contain new weak bands at $470, 325$ and 300 cm^{-1} . These may be assigned to $\nu Hg-OH_2$, $\nu(Hg-Cl)$ and $\nu(Hg-N)$ modes of vibrations, respectively. As 325 cm^{-1} band is the strongest among the three bands, it has been assigned to $\nu(Hg-Cl)$. In monomeric tetrahedral

complexes, $\nu(Hg-Cl)$ (terminal) is observed as a strong band in the 370 cm^{-1} region²⁰ but in linear 4-coordinated polymeric complexes, $\nu(Hg-Cl)$ (terminal) band is observed at 328 cm^{-1} as a strong and broad band²². As the metal-N and metal-S bonds are approximately of the same strength as indicated by equal red and blue shifts of thioamide band IV, $\nu(\text{metal-S})$ mode is expected to be near 200 cm^{-1} . Hence, $\nu(\text{metal-S})$ bands have not been observed.

Thus, the following tentative structures may be assigned to these complexes.

Fig. 1. Probable structure of $\{[Ag(H_2O)_2(DPhTU)]NO_3\}_n$

Fig. 2. Probable structure of $\{[Hg(H_2O)(DPhTU)Cl]Cl\}_n$

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole Complexes with La³⁺, Y³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Gd³⁺, Dy³⁺

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In the present investigation, potentiometric studies on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole and its complexes with some trivalent metal ions have been carried out. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bejerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The titrations were carried out in 75 : 25% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at a constant ionic strength of 0.1 M. Appropriate correction factor for pH meter readings (B values) in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium has been applied².

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DHF mixture for about 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised from DMF to get an analytically pure compound with m.p. 220° . The purity of the compound was established by

tlc and elemental analysis. (Found : C, 63.21 ; H, 4.47 ; N, 10.24. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₆N₂O₄S ; C, 62.71 ; H, 4.51 ; N, 9.98%). The structure of the ligand is,

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal carbonates and perchloric acid of A. R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations³.

Other experimental details were the same as in earlier communication⁴.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned here that the ligand did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 2 hr. This was further confirmed by taking tlc of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

It is the phenolic (OH) group in the ligand which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, Y, the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_d$ values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs $\bar{n}_d$) was plotted. The pK_1 corresponding to phenolic H was obtained by half integral method of $\bar{n}_d = 0.5$. This was further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_d/1 - \bar{n}_d)$ vs B.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}$ and pL values for metal-ligand systems were also determined. From the curves $\bar{n}$ vs pL, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were determined by half integral method. As in the cases of La³⁺, Gd³⁺ and Pr³⁺ complexes, the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was found to be less than 1.78 log units. These were computed by least square method and the same are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF
VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Cations	$t = 25^\circ$						
	H ⁺	Gd ³⁺	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Y ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
$\log K_1$	7.763	8.19	7.90	7.55	5.60	5.90	5.05
$\log K_2$	—	7.13	7.11	7.30	—	—	—

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be Gd³⁺ > La³⁺ > Pr³⁺ > Nd³⁺ > Y³⁺ > Dy³⁺.